

Bixin extraction from annatto seed (*Bixa orellana*) using Ethyl acetate

Arijit Singha, Braja G Bag

Department of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, Vidyasagar University, Paschim Medinipur-721102, WB, India

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received– 05 May, 2019
Revised– 01 May, 2019
Accepted– 17 June, 2019
Available– 29 June, 2019
(online)

Keywords:

Annatto seed
Bixin
Ethyl acetate
Chromatography
1HNMR
GC-MS

Corresponding Author:

Arijit Singha
Email: singhaarijit03@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Bixins, a natural carotenoid pigment, extracted from annatto seed (*Bixa orellana*) has a great commercial application in food, textile, leather and pharmaceutical industries worldwide. In order to extract bixin from annatto seed, magnetic stirring of seeds weighing 4.2 g in ethyl acetate, evaporation and column chromatography of crude pigments using a mixture of ethyl acetate and dichloro methane (3:7) as eluent accompanied with ¹H NMR, GC-MS, UV-spectrophotometric and Fluorescence spectroscopic analysis resulted that the crude solid extract contained 32.1% of bixin. This low per cent due to low performance of column extraction. Extraction methods will be explored cautiously for 100% pigment extraction and purification.

1. Introduction

Bixin (Methylhydrogen-(90Z)-6,60-diapocarotene-6, 60-dioate), an apocarotenoid found in the waxy arils of achiote tree (*Bixa orellana*) seed is extensively used in food industry as colourant and as anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic and analgesic in pharmaceutical industries globally. It is also used in coloring silk and cotton and making hair dye and lip stick of yellow and orange colors. The perennial lipstick tree is distributed worldwide from lowland to mountain with large quantities in Latin America (specially Peru, Brazil and Mexico) which contributes 60% of world commercial production.

The quantity of the bixin and norbixin per seed varies from <1% to >85% depending on the type of solvent extraction (Scotter 2011). This pigment is existed in aril with other minor pigments say – nor-bixin, β-carotene,

cryptoxanthin, lutein, Zeaxanthin and methylbixin (Alves de Lima et al. 2003 ; Figure 1).

Bixin is chemically unstable when isolated from tissue and isomerizes into trans-bixin(Figure 1). It is soluble in fats and alcohol but insoluble in water. In alkaline solution, the methyl ester is hydrolyzed to produce dicarboxylic acid norbixin, a water soluble derivative.

The bixin is conventionally extracted from annatto seed by vegetable oils, alkaline solutions or organic solvents producing low purity accompanied with toxic waste. Taham et al. (2015) reported that pure ethanolic extraction at ambient and high pressure resulted higher concentration of bixin than traditional practices using water and chloroform. Acetone and methanolic extraction yielded the pigment concentration 3.5 – 5.2% (Silva et al. 2008). They also experimentally showed that bixin extraction using supercritical CO₂ magnified the pigment concentration in extract by 10 times. Based on experimental findings, Pattanaik et al. (2018) stated that acetone increased pigment

extraction compared to hexane and methanol. An extraction experiment conducted by Husa et al. (2018) resulted to appear highest pigment concentration (817.7 ppm) in methanol followed by 602.9 ppm in acetone and 477.19 ppm in water. They also observed that the rate of deterioration of bixin was faster in acetone and methanol as compared to water. Melka et al. (2017) used three different solvent mixtures

CHCl₃/EtOH; CHCl₃/Acetone; Hexane/EtOAc and 5% KOH solution and obtained the pigment quantity as much as 9.02%, 4.90%, 2.98% and 26.66%, respectively.

The objective of the study was to investigate the performance of bixin extraction from annatto seeds using the polar solvent mixture of dichloro methane and ethyl acetate.

Fig. 1 Chemical structure of pigments found in the aril of *Bixa orellana* seed

Fig. 2 GPS location of sampling site in Elliot Park, Kolkata (a) and pods of *Bixa orellana* and its seeds (b)

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Sampling site and sample collection

The sample *Bixa orellana* were collected from Elliot Park, Kolkata, West Bengal, India (Fig. 2a). The collected red coloured *Bixa orellana* were shown in figure 2b.

2.2 Extraction

All seeds collected from a single ripen pod weighing 4.2 g were taken in a conical flask of 25ml. Then, 5 ml of ethyl acetate (EA) of analytical reagent grade (Merck, India) was added to it and was stirred magnetically for two hours. It was filtered using Whatman-42 filter paper and the filtrate was collected in a test tube. The mouth of the tube was sealed with Teflon tape.

2.3 Gravimetric analysis

The solvent of the filtrate was evaporated by rotator evaporator and the solid crude was weighed.

2.4 Purification

The crude bixin dissolving in 5 ml of dichloromethane (DCM) was passed through a column of 6cm x 0.6cm measuring the volume of 6.7824 cc packed with silica gel (G60F254; Merck, India) using the eluent mixture of 30% ethyl acetate and dichloromethane (DCM) in the proportion of 3:7. The eluent was determined by performing Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) of the filtrate using different strength of eluents – 10% EA+DCM (1:9), 30% EA+DCM (3:7) and 50% EA+DCM (1:1). Then, column extracts were collected in different test tubes.

2.5 Confirmation of purification

The TLC was performed using column extracts of different test tubes and 30% EA+DCM was used as eluent. The TLC plate of 5cm x 20cm x 2mm was made up of silica gel 60.

2.6 Quantification of purified compound

Purified column extracts were evaporated by rotor evaporator and the purified solids were weighed.

2.7 Compound identification

The purified compound was identified performing ¹HNMR (Varian EM-360) and GC-MS spectroscopy (GCMS-TQ8040 NX, SHIMADZU). The physical properties of bixin were tested by UV (UV-VIS, SHIMADZU) and Fluorescence spectroscopy (SHIMADZU).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Quantification

The acetated extraction of crude bixin from 4.2 g seed was estimated as much as 56 mg whereas; the weight of the purified compound was 18 mg. Therefore, the per cent of bixin in the crude extract and in annatto seed were 32.1% and 0.43%, respectively.

Neither cadmium nor cobalt were observed in the sporocarps of the five. The extraction was low due to low performance of column extraction. Low polarity of ethyl acetate (polarity index – 4.4) optimized pigment extraction from aril. The extraction depended on many influencing factors like –solvent, temperature and geographical source (Pattanaiik et al. 2018). According to Boeing et al. (2014) methanolic extraction was better because of its capability to dissolve both plasma membrane and carotenoid enhancing higher pigment extraction from seed.

3.2 Selection of eluent

Based on TLC performance the eluent mixture 30% EA + DCM (3:7) among 10, 30 and 50% EA + DCM was selected

for column extraction due to its higher resolution (Fig. 3 and 4).

Fig. 3 Resolution of pigments mixture in different eluents in TLC plate. Brighter spot indicates “bixin” pigment

Fig. 4 Column extraction using 30% EA+DCM (3:7)

Fig. 5 TLC yellow spots of bixin of column extracts

Fig. 6 Graphical presentation of 1H NMR of pure extract, peaks analysis and structure formation

3.3 Structure determination and compound identification

TLC of column extract eluted with 30%EA+DCM (3:7) resulted that the Rf value was 0.48 which was same of all pure extracts (Fig. 5).

The peaks analysis of 1H NMR showed that the structure was very much similar to bixin (Fig. 6).GC-Mass Spectra plot revealed that a peak was obtained at the region of 394 that

was same to the mass of pure bixin (Mass- 394.214409 Da). UV-irradiation resulted in the occurrences of two absorption peaks at 456 nm and 482 nm respectively (Fig. 8 and Table 1). Fluoro-photometric analysis with irradiation of waves of 450 nm exhibited that a fluorescence peak appeared at 535nm (Fig. 9). Therefore, this pure compound must be “bixin”.

Fig. 7 GC-Mass Spectra plot

Fig. 8 UV absorbance graph of pure extract.

Fig. 9 Fluorescence plot of pure extract when irradiated with 450 nm waves.

Table 1 UV spectrometric data of pure extract

λ_{max} { nm}	Length{cm}	Absorbance	Conc.{mol/L}	Extinction co-efficient { ϵ }{L/mol.cm}
482	0.2	0.932	7.95×10^{-5}	5.86×10^4
456	0.2	1.057	7.95×10^{-5}	6.65×10^4

4. Conclusion

The present study concluded the followings:

- The pure extract is bixin.
- The physical properties of bixin are not altered in ethyl acetated extraction.
- The aril of annatto seed contains 32.1% bixin.
- The extraction efficiency must be improved.
- For commercial utilization in textile and leather, more researches are need on annatto dye chemistry.
- The extraction methods need to be further explored in order to exploit full potential of this natural dye.
- Action mechanism of bixin in biological tissue must be explored as a further study.

References

- Alves de Lima RO, Azevedo L, Ribeiro RL, Salvadori DMF (2003) Study on the mutagenicity and antimutagenicity of a natural food colour (annatto) in mouse bone marrow cells. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 41 (2): 189 – 192.
- Boeing JS, Barizão EO, E Silva BC, Montanher PF, de Cinque Almeida V, Visentainer JV (2014) Evaluation of solvent effect on the extraction of phenolic compounds and antioxidant capacities from the berries: application of principal component analysis. *Chemistry Central Journal* 8(1): 48. doi: 10.1186/s13065-014-0048-1
- Husa NN, Hamzah F, Said HM (2018) Characterization and Storage Stability Study of Bixin Extracted from *Bixaorellana* Using Organic Solvent. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 358: 012035. doi:10.1088/1757-899X/358/1/012035
- Melka B, Bisrat D, NeelaiahBabu G (2017) Isolation, Characterization and Biological Activities of Food Colorants from *Bixaorellana*. *Journal of Pharmacovigilance* 5(4): 237. doi:10.4172/2329-6887.1000237
- Pattanaik L, Pradhan S, Shaoo NK, Naik SN (2018) Extraction and rapid quantification of pure bixin from *Bixaorellana* L. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources* 9(4): 290 – 295.
- Scotter MJ (2011) Methods for the determination of European Union-permitted added natural colours in foods: a review. *Food Additives & Contaminants* 28: 527–596. doi: 10.1080/19440049.2011.555844
- Silva GF, Gamarra FMC, Oliveira AL, Cabral FA (2008) Extraction of bixin from annatto seeds using super critical carbon dioxide. *Brazilian Journal of Chemical Engineering* 25(2): 419 – 426.
- Taham T, Cabral FA, Barrozo MAS (2015) Extraction of bixin from annatto seeds using combined technologies. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids* 100: 175 – 183.